

A Study on Attitude of Undergraduate MBBS Students towards Different Teaching Methods

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Abstract:

Aim: The study was conducted in order to evaluate the attitude of I year Undergraduate Medical students towards various methods used for teaching in Medicine.

Materials and Methods: The first year Medical students of Government Sivagangai Medical College were recruited for the study. A questionnaire prepared with relevant questions, was circulated among the participants, collected back and the results with analyzed using descriptive statistics.

Results: Out of 100 students involved in the study, 82 % of the students felt that powerpoint presentations with videos help them to understand the concepts better. About two thirds of the students find it difficult to see the words written on the blackboard.50% of the students felt that there should be small group discussion at the end of each session.

Conclusion: The study gives an insight into various teaching methodologies based on students' perspective which will help us to improve our teaching methods in future.

Keywords: Medical Students, Power Point, Small Group Discussion.

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Introduction

It is a right of every Indian citizen to get the basic health care of good standard. This is possible only if the 'Physicians of first contact' are given proper Medical Education and made competent enough to meet the health needs of the country. The current competency based medical education gives utmost importance to reviewing the teaching and assessment methods at regular intervals. [1] Feedback from students plays an important role in developing new teaching and assessment strategies. [2] Also obtaining feedback from students is an inexpensive and easily available way to bridge the communication gap between faculties and students.[3]

Objective of the Study

The Study was conducted to evaluate the attitude of undergraduate medical students towards various methods of teaching used in medicine

Materials and Methods

This is an observational study conducted in the Department of Biochemistry involving 100 First

year Undergraduate Medical students. There were 60 females and 40 male students involved in the study. The study was conducted during regular teaching hours. A questionnaire was prepared with relevant questions to evaluate the attitude of under

graduate Medical students towards various teaching methods. Informed consent was obtained from the participants prior to the study and it was taken care that the identity of the students was not revealed. The students were explained about the instructions to fill up the questionnaire. The questionnaires were then distributed and 30 minutes were given to fill up the responses. At the end of 30 minutes, the response sheets were collected. The results were expressed using descriptive statistics. The internal consistency of the questionnaire was assessed by testing Chronbach alpha, Data analysis was done using SPSS software version 16.

Results

Of the 100 participants involved in the study, 60% were females and the rest were male students.

Majority of the students prefer powerpoint presentations over blackboard teaching. 82 % of the students feel that powerpoint presentations with videos help them to understand the concepts better (Figure 1). Animations are liked by 71% of the

participants as they make the session lively and interesting (Figure 2). About two-third of the students find it difficult to see the words written on the blackboard. 50% of the students felt that there should be small group discussion at the end of each session.

PPT with Videos are useful

Figure1: Usefulness of PPT with videos

Figure 2: Effect of Animations on Classroom teaching

Discussion

The study helps us to understand the attitude of first year MBBS students towards various teaching methodologies used in medical education. With the advances in technology, Powerpoint presentations have a clear edge over black board teaching as far as the students are concerned. Incorporation of videos to explain the concepts and performance of clinical skills is very much appreciated by the students. Use of animations during Powerpoint presentations are believed to make the session lively and interesting. Though interactive, the main drawback of blackboard teaching is that the words written are often not legible. This creates gaps in understanding the concepts clearly. Small group discussion at the end of the class was wanted by

many students. This will help in clarification of the doubts and better retention of the topic. Our study shows that in the present era, medical students prefer power point presentation with advances such as video assisted learning and animation for better understanding and retention of the theoretical concepts, and skilful learning of the practical procedures for efficient use in the future.

Conclusion

Obtaining feedback is a key feature of formative assessment used in current competency based curriculum. Feedback from students is important to review the teaching methods used in Medical Education.[4] We recommend that all medical Institutions should carry out evaluation of students' responses to various teaching methodologies.

Incorporation of these would bring a major change in Medical Education, making it more innovative and producing competent doctors to serve the community in a better way.

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